

Impacts of Online Class to the Student's Achievement in the Prototyping Class: A Qualitative Study of Entrepreneurship Online Classes During the Pandemic

Gatot Hendra Prakoso¹, Indriana¹, Stievan K. Halim¹, Indira Tyas W¹, Siti Paramadita¹, Rosalin Ayal¹, Hans Daniel¹, Aloysius Bernanda Gunawan², Ira Setyawati³

¹Binus Entrepreneurship Center, Indonesia

²Marketing Communication Department, Bina Nusantara University, Indonesia

³Management Department, Bina Nusantara University, Indonesia

Email: gprakosa@binus.edu

Abstract

Online education is a mandatory condition for any education institution at the pandemic, including in the higher education institution. In the entrepreneurship education is also should be delivered by online, including the prototyping classes, which normally is being delivered offline. This study were conducted to investigate how the prototyping could be developed within the prototyping classrooms, which were being done through online. We found that two factors: the lecturers' perspective of how far the prototype should be developed and the prototype-business type relation.

Keywords: *Online Education, Prototyping, Lecturers.*

INTRODUCTION

It remains unclear when the pandemic would be ended. Yet, all the processes in life should be gone back into 'normal'. As we all have known, things were switched onto the online world, including in the education field. (Tarkar, 2020) stated that because of the pandemic, schools and colleges, and also universities should be closed. That decision certainly impacted the whole education system. Similar idea also stated by (Rashid & Yadav, 2020).

Entrepreneurship education is one of the parts of the education field that had to be exposed by the impact of the pandemic. Normally, entrepreneurship education would involve lots of activities that should be done out of the classrooms (Izquierdo, n.d.; Usman & Raharjo, 2021). Since the pandemic attacks, things should be done online, including the entrepreneurship education, which definitely, created certain hurdles for the lecturers and the students as well (Rashid & Yadav, 2020).

Entrepreneurship education itself, was being delivered in many various ways and systems. Most of those were basically being done with less of theoretical aspects – which only being used as the foundations of the students to do the practical aspects, which would be the dominant part of the entrepreneurship classes (Izquierdo, n.d.). In some universities, entrepreneurship were being taught in several steps, which were being divided into several subjects (Valerio et al., 2014; Winkel & Vanevenhoven, 2013). For instance, (Boldureanu et al., 2020).

One of the entrepreneurship classes is the entrepreneurship prototyping classes. It could appear in many kinds of names such as prototyping class, prototype development class, prototype creation class (Noyes, 2018; Reagle et al., 2017), etc, depends on the institutions that were applying it into their curriculums.

It is quite intriguing to discuss about prototyping process, and the prototype itself. The definition of it could be varies (Houde & Hill, 1997; Kim, 2019). This study was being developed to investigate the result that appeared from the entrepreneurship prototyping classes in a higher education institution in Jakarta, Indonesia. The result of this study could give us the new insight on how prototype is being defined – from the classroom, in the entrepreneurship classes, by using the entrepreneurship education perspective, and how the definition of the prototype could bring the result into more developable result, which certainly, would be closer to the market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Prototype and Prototyping Definition

There are various definitions of prototype and prototyping definitions that came up from various researchers. According to (Houde & Hill, 1997), prototype is the representation of a design idea. It does not matter what kind of medium that

were being used to develop it. This definition would cover the preexisting object when it was being used to answer a design question.

A prototype is considerably as the physical embodiment of the critical elements in the design. Prototype is also the iterative tool in term of enhancing and decision making throughout the design process (C. Lauff et al., 2017). Furthermore, (C. A. Lauff & Kotys-schwartz, 2018) stated that prototype are the tools for enhancing the communication, increasing learning, and informing the decision making.

Prototype was mentioned as the first step toward an entrepreneurial initiative. It is necessary to elicit long term interest in term of continuing the business idea (C. A. Lauff & Kotys-schwartz, 2018). (Odom et al., 2016) stated that prototypes are assumed as the part of the path to the fully realized commercial product, which was intended to be the testing product to see the functions of the specified needs, or perhaps the unmet requirements.

According to (Osann et al., 2020), prototype were categorized into three level; low, medium and high details. The prototype methods are varies from the sketch (which is considered as low detail) to the minimum viable product – MVP (which is considered as high detail prototype). Meanwhile, prototyping is considered as the one of so many possible ways to reduce the possible errors in the design and to eliminate the failure factors within the initial design phase (Kim, 2019). A bold statement was stated by (C. A. Lauff & Kotys-schwartz, 2018) by stating that prototyping is the essential part of product development in companies, yet, less exploration were being done in this phase among all areas of design practice.

Prototyping is the process to put together the working models (prototypes) in term of representing the ideas, to test the various aspects of a design, and also, most importantly, to gather the customer feedback. It would help the entrepreneur to develop, test and refine the business ideas within such short period, to make a confirmation on an opportunity (Noyes, 2018).

According to (Camburn et al., 2017) prototyping is connected to all products, service and systems development efforts. It determines a huge portion of the development process and has influences in the successfulness of the design project.

The aim of prototyping is not only specifically to product invention, but also to have a broader exploration and evaluation for the potential opportunities. It is also could be used to explore service ideas or service experiences, product-service combinations, and also business model concepts (Reagle et al., 2017).

Online Class and Student's Acceptance

As we have mentioned earlier in the introduction section, the pandemic forced all aspects in the world to go online, including the education section (Dogar et al., 2020; Tarkar, 2020). Certainly, this condition has certain impacts. The pros stated that the online learning method is something that should have done long ago due to several aspects, including efficiency (Smart & Cappel, 2006).

Online learning was considered as beneficial since it could give the opportunity to give much wider access to anyone, without boundaries, claimed to have better and more improved quality of learning, gave the students the chances to get more prepared, and also provided a lifelong learning opportunity (Appana, 2008).

(Kahiigi et al., 2008) cited by (Qahmash, 2013) stated that online learning would give the chances for the educators to monitor the class, compared to the traditional courses. It also given the opportunity to interact through emails. Moreover, it was considerably more efficient on the cost stand point.

However, some studies stated differently. (Adnan & Anwar, 2020) stated that even it was the best way to prevent the possibilities of being exposed by the pandemic, yet it did not give positive impacts in term of the result. It was considered not as effective as the conventional learning.

Technological aspects were also taken part of the concerns. According to (Dogar et al., 2020), the poor connectivity of the internet gave certain issues since it caused the communication to be ineffective. It was also stated that the over exposure to the screen might have negative impacts in the future. One of the most concerned aspects amongst it all is the face-to-face human contact aspect, which did not appear in the virtual classroom. It might have the negative impact such as reducing the sense of belonging of the students, and also reducing their participation in the class (Mcbrien et al., 2021).

Despite the constraints, the positive acceptance occurred from the students. According to (Adnan & Anwar, 2020) the acceptability of the students is increasing from time to time. The students also considered some positive dimensions of the online learning. Another positive information came from (Adnan & Anwar, 2020) that stated the students stated that they felt they were qualified to use the computers for the online classes, yet they felt that conventional classes were considerably more effective.

The study from (Dahalan et al., 2012) showed that learners attitude might have the impacts to the student’s engagement in the online classrooms. The attitude (Dahalan et al., 2012) continues, play a role in predicting the e-mentoring. Their perceptions to the teacher also have the important part to determine the result. The more comfortable the learner might be, the more they have the willingness to be involved in the classroom.

METHOD

As this is a qualitative-research, we chose to use the in-depth interview method to gain the information of the informant. To support this research, we chose informants. Those informants were chosen based on the purposive sampling method. Based on the existence condition, we have 47 potential candidates for the informant. Those 47 potential candidates are the entrepreneurship lectures in a higher education institution in Jakarta, Indonesia. We went deeper to the profiles of the candidates, and we found that three lecturers were on sabbatical leave for the last two semesters, which means they were automatically eliminated from the potential candidates’ list. We have 44 potential candidates left.

Furthermore, we found that 14 out of 44 were the newly recruited lecturers, which mean they had no experiences on handling the entrepreneurship prototyping classes. Therefore, we had 30 potential candidates left. Then, we went further to the historical data of those 30 potential candidates, and we found that there were only 12 lecturers that have already deliver the prototyping classes during the pandemic, through the online classrooms.

These 12 lecturers are considered as the suitable candidates for the informants of this study. These 12 lecturers are matched to the criteria that were made by the researchers; which are: 1) entrepreneurship lecturers, 2) teaching the prototyping subjects during pandemics and 3) the lecturer’s definition of Prototype.

A series of in-deph interview through the online media (zoom, phone calls) were being conducted to those 12 informants to gather the necessary data for this research.

We analyze the data by adapting the data analysis method from (Cox et al., 2009). In a brief explanation, these are the steps that should be taken to get the result from this study. The data that was taken from the interviews were being triangulated with the observational data and archival data.

Figure 1. Data Analysis Flow

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the review on the triangulated data (the interview data; observational data and the archival data), there are three things that came up to the spotlights. Those three things were: 1) lecturers perceptions on prototype – which would directly related to the result of the prototyping process; 2) the prototype – business type relations; and 3) the students’ achivement of prototyping – which would be shown by the end result of the prototype after the class ended.

Lecturers Perceptions on Prototype

The interview, compared with the other data stated that the prototyping classes’ direction was also determined by the perceptions of the lecturers. Based on the interview, we found that there were no uniformities on the prototype perceptions among those participants. The non-uniformity were detected by the facts that those lecturers have different ‘end-point’ standards for the prototype that should be developed by their students in the classrooms.

The lecturers even have the different opinion on their own classrooms when it is related to the technology-based business and non-technology based prototype. Two informants stated that they have different types of prototype achievements in the classrooms. The non-technology-based business, which were mainly the f&b business, succeeded to achieve the MVP version, since they have asked the students to do so.

All informant stated that they urged the students to develop the f&b business idea to the MVP level, or they could not pass the prototyping classrooms. The different treatments were applied to the students that have chosen the technology-based business ideas. All informants agreed that it was almost impossible for the students to reach the MVP level. Nevertheless, the informants have dissenting opinions on the minimum level of the technology-based business prototype. Five informants stated that they pushed the students to have at least the working UI – by allowing the students to use the online freeware to develop the prototype. Six informants told the students to have at least the mock-up, that could give the clear descriptions on how the application should be. Only one informant that allow the students to develop the sketch for their application, but the sketch should be completed with the information of each function of the application's features.

The Prototype-business type relations

The entrepreneurship classrooms in this research's objects were taken by all study programs. Therefore, three specific conditions occurred. Those conditions are based on the different nature of each study program, and the different nature of the students as well. Those conditions are: i) mixed (study programs) classroom vs homogeneous classrooms, ii) technology based classrooms vs non-technology-based classrooms and iii) the business type of the students groups.

Mixed (study programs) classroom vs homogeneous classrooms

The mixed classrooms might consist of students from various study programs – for instance, students from chinese literature, management, and civil engineering were mixed into a prototyping class. This type of classrooms – according to the informants, might have certain obstacles in term of developing their business ideas – which came from the different classrooms in the earlier semester. The students had to determine, which one of the business ideas – amongst those three study programs that would be developed into the prototype. Normally, the informants stated that the students would decided to choose the business ideas that considerably as the simplest one to be developed.

Though the homogeneous classrooms were contained of single type study programs, the complexity might occur because of the other certain conditions. Since the prototyping class is the continuation of the ideation class – which should be taken by each student on their prior semester, the prototyping classrooms might be containing of students from different ideation classrooms, eventhough they were from the same study programs. Therefore, the similar complexity occurred. They had to decide, which business ideas would be developed as prototype.

Technology based classrooms vs non-technology-based classrooms

The technology based classrooms would mainly put their business ideas on the technology based products. Most of them chose the application concepts as their business ideas in the ideation classrooms. When they were in the prototyping classrooms, would choose one of the business ideas that where considerably the simplest one to be build into prototype.

The non-technology-based classrooms, if it was the homogeneous classrooms, would tend to choose the food and beverage (f&b) business, fashion business, or consultancy-based business. Amongst those three types of chosen businesses, the f&b was likely to be the one that was chosen the most.

The business type of the students groups

Business type is one considerably the most determining factors of how the prototype could be developed or not. The lecturers – according to the informants were restricted to some rules. One of the rules are the students were only able to develop four types of businesses; 1) f&B; 2) creative; 3) social-based business; and 4) techno-based business. Therefore, the students should chose one of those business types.

Amongst those business types, the f&b business is the most chosen one. According to the informants this business is the simplest one to develop. The informants stated that for the students that chose the tecnology-based business, it was impossible for them to develop an MVP for their apps. They have certain limitations – other than times to develop, such as lack of coding capabilities and lack of relations to certain related parties for the apps. The students that decided to develop the f&b and creative businesses have relatively simpler steps to develop their prototype, even to the MVP.

The students' achievements of prototyping

Based on the informants' information, compared to the archival data, the researchers found that by the end of the prototyping classes, there were varies of achievement levels of the prototyping. The technology-based business ideas

were varies between mockup to the simple versions of UI – made by using the online freeware. None of those technology-based business ideas were able to achieve the MVP level, due to varies reasons.

Almost all of the non-technology-based business ideas (f&B, creative and social business) were able to develop the prototype on the MVP level. The exception went to social business that should be developed through apps – and it is considered as the technology-based business.

All informants (12 informants) agreed that the f&b business is the business type that were the simplest one to be developed into prototype, and they stated that all students in their classrooms have managed to developed their final prototype version – which would be ready to be validated soon.

CONCLUSIONS

After comparing the information from all informants, it is safe to state that the prototyping end result were achieved based on two conditions. *One*, the lecturers' perspective, which would lead the informants (as lecturers) to urge the students to the level that they wanted to achieve. Informants have different perspective of how the prototype should be developed, and what kind of end-product of the prototype should be. Therefore, the prototype results were considerably varies; from sketch to the MVP version. *Two*, the *Prototype-business type relations*. A certain business type might have the bigger chances (which means easier) to reach the MVP level, for instance, the f&b business. On the other hand, the technology-based business such application-based business were unlikely to reach the MVP level, due to the certain conditions, such as lack of coding capabilities and the lack of time to develop. Those two factors are the determining factors of how “high” the prototype could be achieved.

This study was conducted only in a single higher education institution. Certain unique characteristics might occur in this place that only represents itself. Therefore, certain unique conditions might happen if the similar study is being done in any other places, in any other levels of educations.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Adnan, M., & Anwar, K. (2020). *Online learning amid the COVID-19 pandemic : Students ' perspectives*. 2(1), 2–8.
- [2]. Appana, S. (2008). A Review of Benefits and Limitations of Online Learning in the Context of the Student , the Instructor , and the Tenured Faculty. *International Journal on E-Learning*, 7, 5–22.
- [3]. Boldureanu, G., Ionescu, A. M., Bercu, A. M., Bedrule-Grigoruță, M. V., & Boldureanu, D. (2020). Entrepreneurship education through successful entrepreneurial models in higher education institutions. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12031267>
- [4]. Camburn, B., Viswanathan, V., Linsey, J., Anderson, D., Jensen, D., Crawford, R., Otto, K., & Wood, K. (2017). Design prototyping methods : state of the art in strategies , techniques , and guidelines. *Design Science, Schrage 1993*, 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1017/dsj.2017.10>
- [5]. Cox, E., Davis, J., Greenstein, S., Hillman, A., Katila, R., & Ocasio, W. (2009). Origin of Alliance Portfolios : Entrepreneurs, Network Strategies, and Firm Performance. *Academy of Management*, 52(2), 246–279.
- [6]. Dahalan, N., Hassan, H., & Atan, H. (2012). Student Engagement in Online Learning : Learners Attitude Toward E-Mentoring. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 67(November 2011), 464–475. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.11.351>
- [7]. Dogar, A. A., Shah, I., & Ali, S. W. (2020). *Constraints to Online Teaching in Institutes of Higher Education during Pandemic COVID- 19 : A Case Study of CUI , Abbottabad Pakistan*. 12, 12–24.
- [8]. Houde, S., & Hill, C. (1997). *What do Prototypes Prototype ?*
- [9]. Izquierdo, E. (n.d.). *What Entrepreneurial Competencies should be emphasized in Entrepreneurship and Innovation Education at the Under ...*
- [10]. Kahiigi, E. K., Ekenberg, L., Hansson, H., & Tusubira, F. F. (2008). Exploring the e-Learning State of art Exploring the e-Learning State of Art. *Electronic Journal of E-Learning*, May 2014.
- [11]. Kim, D. Y. (2019). *A Design Methodology Using Prototyping Based on the Digital-Physical Models in the Architectural Design Process*.
- [12]. Lauff, C. A., & Kotys-schwartz, D. (2018). *What is a Prototype ? What are the Roles of Prototypes in Companies ? October*. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4039340>
- [13]. Lauff, C., Kotys-schwartz, D., & Rentschler, M. (2017). What is a Prototype ? : Emergent Roles of Prototypes From Empirical Work in Three Diverse Companies. *Journal of Mechanical Design*, August. <https://doi.org/10.1115/DETC2017-67173>
- [14]. McBrien, J. L., Cheng, R., & Jones, P. (2021). Virtual Spaces : Employing a Synchronous Online Classroom to Facilitate Student Engagement in Online Learning Virtual Spaces : Employing a Synchronous Online Classroom to Facilitate Student Engagement in Online Learning. *International Review on Research in Open and Distributed*

Learning.

- [15]. Noyes, E. (2018). *Teaching Entrepreneurial Action Through Prototyping: The Prototype-It Challenge*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2515127417737289>
- [16]. Odom, W., Wakkary, R., Lim, Y., Desjardins, A., Hengeveld, B., & Banks, R. (2016). From Research Prototype to Research Product. *Interventions to Design Theory*.
- [17]. Osann, I., Mayer, L., & Wiele, I. (2020). *DESIGN THINKING*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [18]. Qahmash, A. (2013). The Benefits and Barriers of E-learning in Higher Education in Saudi Arabia The Benefits and Barriers of E-learning in Higher Education in Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Journal of Educational Technology Research*, May.
- [19]. Rashid, S., & Yadav, S. S. (2020). Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Higher Education and Research. In *Indian Journal of Human Development* (Vol. 14, Issue 2, pp. 340–343). Sage Publications India Pvt. Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0973703020946700>
- [20]. Reagle, C., Maggioni, V., Boicu, M., Albanese, M., Joshi, M., & Sklarew, D. (2017). *From Idea to Prototype: Introducing Students to Entrepreneurship*. March 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISECon.2017.7910251>
- [21]. Smart, K. L., & Cappel, J. J. (2006). *Students' Perceptions of Online Learning: A Comparative Study*. 5.
- [22]. Tarkar, P. (2020). Impact Of Covid-19 Pandemic On Education System Role of education in future prospects after retirement View project Impact Of Covid-19 Pandemic On Education System. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(9s), 3812–3814. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352647439>
- [23]. Usman, H., & Raharjo, N. E. (2021). Model Pendidikan Karakter Kewirausahaan di Sekolah Menengah Kejuruan. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Teknologi Kejuruan*, 140–147.
- [24]. Valerio, A., Parton, B., & Robb, A. (2014). *Entrepreneurship Education and Training Programs around the World*.
- [25]. Winkel, D., & Vanevenhoven, J. (2013). The Structure and Scope of Entrepreneurship Programs in Higher Education Around the World. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*.